

IN VITRO STUDY OF ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF PADMAK AGAD AGAINST DERMATOPHYTE

Shilpa Gawande Kolarkar^{1*} and Tushar Khairnar²

¹MD Agadtantra Department, Carc Akurdi, Pune.

²Associate Professor, Agadtantra department, Carc Akurdi, Pune.

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***Corresponding Author**

**Dr. Shilpa Gawande
Kolarkar**

MD Agadtantra Department,
Carc Akurdi, Pune.

ABSTRACT

Background Lesions of *Dadru* or *Tinea* are also similar to spider bite lesions hence *Padmak agad* (Antitoxic formulation); mentioned in the treatment of the same used here in study. *Aims and objectives* to find an alternative therapy which will reduce rate of relapse and recurrence of fungal infection. *Methods* Contents of *Padmak agad* were mixed with water and soaked overnight, filtrate sterilized and used for the study. Zone of inhibition of growth of the fungus was observed and compared with standard. *Results* Zone of inhibition formed due to *Padmak agad* was 11mm whereas due to control drug was

30mm. *Observations* though the contents formulation did not dissolve completely; the filtrate shows antifungal activity. *Discussion* Filtrate showed minimal antifungal activity in comparison with the control Fluconazole

1. As the coarse powder soaked more water and did not dissolve completely hence, the concentration achieved was dilute in comparison with the standard.
2. Test drug can show more inhibition zone if extracts of it is used.
3. *Trichophyton mentagrophyte* is the most resistant fungus species.
4. Due to filtration process many active constituents may have not participated in the activity study.
5. Sterilization might have hampered thermolabile chemical constituents showing minimal antifungal activity of *Padmak agad*.

KEYWORDS:- *Padmak Agad*, Dermatophyte, Antifungal, in-vitro, Fluconazole, *Tinea*.

1. INTRODUCTION

In India, the prevalence of therapy-refractory superficial dermatophytosis and chronic relapsing disease has increased significantly during the past 5–6 years. Recently, there has been a noticeable transition from *Trichophyton rubrum* to *Trichophyton mentagrophyte* in India. The "Indian ITS genotype," which is only seen in *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* and may spread, was also discovered through sequencing. In India, OTC treatments that mix antifungal and antibacterial antibiotics with topical clobetasol and other steroid chemicals are frequently abused.^[1] Dermatophytosis is the most typical cause of Dadru.^[2] The Ayurvedic branch Agadtantra deals with various intoxications and their treatment. One of the many different varieties of venoms is *luta visha*, or spider venom. In a separate chapter devoted to treating *lutavisha*, Sushrutacharya and Ashtanghridaykar discuss the diagnostic symptoms and numerous *kalpas*, or medicine formulations, used to treat spider venom. Spider venom can actually cause lesions on the skin that mimic ringworm or *Tinea* sores when it comes into contact with the skin.

Dadru a kind of skin disease that is *Kushtha* described in Ayurved literature resembles Ringworm or *Tinea*. Previously, it was discovered that the principles of *luta dansha* might be used to treat *Visarpa*.^[3] We propose to apply the same principle in this case.

Padmak Agad which mentioned by *Vagbhat* in *Lootavisha* treatment, here we have used the *Agad* to carry out antifungal assay against the fungus causing *tinea* named *Trichophyton montagrophyte*.

Table 1: Similarities between Signs and Symptoms *Dadru* and *Luta Dansha*.^[4,5,6] (Original).

<i>Luta dansha</i>	<i>Dadru kushth</i>	<i>Tinea/dermatophytosis</i>
<i>Mandal</i> (Round bordered lesion)	Yes	Yes
<i>Unnat</i> (Hived)	Yes (<i>Pidikanvat</i>)	Yes
<i>Visarpavan</i>	<i>Visarpin</i>	Yes (<i>Spreads</i>)
<i>Shof</i> (Inflammation)	Yes	Yes
<i>Madhye krushna athava shyaav</i>	<i>Atasipushp varna</i>	Lichenified
<i>Kandu</i> (Itching)	Yes	Yes
<i>Yatsprushyate angam kurute vranam</i>	<i>Anushangini</i>	<i>Infection spreads when filaments touch normal part</i>

2. Rationale of the study

Latest studies on epidemiology of dermatophytic infections from different parts of India, rise in the prevalence of cutaneous dermatophytosis which has uncommon infection with increased spectrum^[7] 8 weeks After the initial episode of infection when standard allopathic treatment was given it got relapsed.^[8]

This shows that the Patients exhibit resistance to standard antifungal medicines which are used as a regular part of treatment.^[9]

a) It is need of time to find an alternative therapy which will reduce rate of relapse and recurrence in patients. Hence this study is undertaken to apply principles of *Agadatantra* in this scenario.

This study will be done on available culture in a renowned laboratory.

b) No previous study has been done to access the antifungal susceptibility of dermatophyte towards *Padmak Agad*.

c) In case of positive outcome of this study animal experiments and clinical trials may be carried out in future.

3. Aims

-To evaluate the antifungal activity of *Padmak Agad* contents collectively.

-To compile *Ayurvedic* and modern literature on *Padmak Agad*

-To collect and compile ayurvedic and modern literature on *Dadru* and *Tinea*.

-To evaluate the efficacy of aqueous solution of *Padmak Agad* as an antifungal on cultured fungus.

-To record and evaluate the data scientifically with the help of charts, diagrams, photographs.

-To establish evidence of antifungal activity of *Padmak Agad* so it could further be used for clinical trial in *Dadru* or *Tinea* patients.

4. Objective

Study in Vitro antifungal activity of *Padmak Agad* against the most recurrence causing dermatophyte *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*.

Table 2: Previous work done (Original).

Author	Title	Publication/year
Bhumkar dhiraj gorakhnath et al.	conceptual study of anti-toxic effect of padmak agad-a review ^[10]	iamj volume7, issue 3, march 2019

Murugsh j et al ^[11]	evaluation of the antifungal efficacy of different concentrations of curcuma longa on candida albicans: an in vitro study	Jomfp,2019
Mitesh et.al	experiment study on efficacy of padmakgada lepa in honey-bee sting ^[12]	Ijpsr ,2017
Mehar manjusha m. Et al	effect of padmakagadalepa incontact poisoning of bhallataka ^[13]	Iamj,2017
Pauline mcloone et al	honey: a realistic antimicrobial for disorders of the skin ^[14]	Journal of microbiology 2016
Kaushik et al	therapeutic potentials of cow derived products- a review	Ijpsr, 2016
Pandey ajay s.et al	callicarpa macrophylla: a review of its phyto-chemistry, pharmacology	Folklore claims, and ayurvedic studies, 2014
Mathur abhishek et al	antifungal activity of some plant extracts against clinical pathogens.	Adv. Appl. Sci. Res., 2011

WHO has included Tinea or ringworm under Communicable Diseases (CDS) and the Water, Sanitation and Health unit (WSH).

5. MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

a. Material

For this experimental study following herbs were used

Table 5: Chemical composition.

-Drug name	Chemical composition
Callicarpa macrophylla	Tannins, fruit oils contain selinene fruit oils found rich in selinene derivatives. The fruit oil is comprised of 41.6% beta-selinene and 6% alpha-selinene. Dendrolasin
Curcuma longa	Curcumin, essential oil contains d-phellanderene, sabinene, cincol, borneol, zingiberene, sesquiterpenes.
Berberis aristate	Berberine, aromolin, barbamin, columbamine, karachine, oxyberberin, Taxilamine
Honey	Fructose, Glucose, sucrose, minerals protiens, Amino acids
Ghee	Saturated fats, Monosaturated fats, Polysaturated fats

1. *Haridra* and *Daruharidra* rhizomes were procured from local wholesale dealer. *Priyangu* seeds were procured online. *Priyangu* and *Haridra* were got authenticated by authorised research laboratory.
2. The coarse powders of *Haridra*, *Daruharidra* and *Priyangu* was prepared by grinding the seeds.
3. Mixture of contents that is *Padmak Agad* was standardized at authorised laboratory.
4. Dermatophyte –Cell line of Dermatophyte *Trichophyton mentagrophyte* was procured from authorised source.
5. Medium for culture-Medium for culture- Fungus culture was grown in the advised culture that is 53 SDA (Sabouraud'S Dextrose Agar medium) at authorised laboratory.
6. Standard antifungal used: Fluconazole injection USP 2mg/ml, B No. A410278, MFD July 21, Exp Jun24.

Fig. 1: Culture – *Trichophyton mentagrophyte* (Original).

6. METHODOLOGY

Fig. 2: Methodology.

Preparation of test sample: Padmak agad

Haridra 3.0 gm + Daruharidra 3.0 gm + Priyangu 3.0 gm mixed properly and extracted in 50ml sterile distilled water and stirred on magnetic stirrer for 30 minutes. This mixture is kept for 24 hours. Filtered through Whatman paper no. 40. Filtrate is passed through micron filtration syringe. Filtrate is collected in sterile glass vial and sterilized in autoclave for 15 minutes at 121°C and 15 Lb pressure. Padmak Agad filtrate is used for antifungal activity.

Extract description: Yellow colour clear liquid

Incubation and Temperature control

For fungal cultural growth 30°C

Test antifungal activity

Method Agar Well diffusion

Culture used *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* MCC 1566

Medium Sabaroud's Dextrose Agar 20ml/plate

Standard Solution Fluconazole 2mg/ml

Qty used 200µ/well

Test Solution -200µ/well

All inoculated plates with standard and test material were kept in refrigerator for diffusion for 4 hours. Then plates were incubated in BOD at 24°C for growth of fungus and shows inhibition zone of test and standard material after 48 to 72 hours.

7. OBSERVATIONS AND RESULT

1. Among all contents of Coarse powder of Padmak Agad, Priyangu absorbed more water Hence, needed to add more water to get the aqueous solution.
2. We got yellow coloured clear liquid as aqueous solution.
3. Dermatophyte took 3 weeks to grow.
4. Being aqueous solution the test sample after pouring on dermatophyte, the solution itself got contaminated hence needed to be sterilized.
5. Sterilized aqueous solution showed minimal antifungal activity.
6. Standard drug Fluconazole showed maximum antifungal activity.

Fig. 3: Zone of inhibition formed by Padmak Agad and Fluconazole. (Original)

Result

Standard Zone Diameter 30mm.

Test Zone Diameter 11.2mm.

8. CONCLUSION

Padmak Agad having antifungal activity against *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* MCC 1566.

9. DISCUSSION

Table 3: Padmak agad Contents and Their action. (Original)

Drug Name	Solvent	Proven Action	Fungus
1. <i>Priyangu</i> ^[15] (<i>Gandhapriyangu</i>) L.N.- <i>Callicarpa macrophylla</i> Vahl.	alcohol	Antifungal	<i>Alternaria alternata</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Cladosporium cladosporidies</i> , <i>Drechslera halodes</i> and <i>Fusarium moniliform</i> <i>Alternaria alternata</i> , <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i> , <i>Cladosporium cladosporidies</i> , <i>Drechslera halodes</i> and <i>Fusarium moniliform</i>
2. <i>Haridra</i> ^[11] L.N.- <i>Curcuma longa</i> Linn.	Alcoholic extract	Antifungal	<i>Candida</i>
3. <i>Daruharidra</i> ^[16] L.N.- <i>Berberis aristata</i> DC	Ethanollic and aqueous extract	Antifungal	<i>estalotiopsis theae</i> . (Saw.) Stey., <i>Colletotrichum camelliae</i> . Mess., <i>Curvularia eragrostidis</i> . (P. Hennings) Meyer, and <i>Botryodiplodia theobromae</i>

The above table proves *Padmak Agad* contents have individually shown antifungal activity with solvents other than water. Hence minimal antifungal activity of *Padmak Agad* which is due to combined less solubility of contents of *Padmak Agad* in water.

As the contents of *Padmak Agad* were not completely dissolved in water this preparation is called as *Hima Kalpana* (cold infusion) of Ayurvedic formulation as per *Sharangdhar Madhyam Khanda 4/1*

Trichophyton mentagrophyte is the genotype in India responsible for the recurrence of the disease. This is one of most resistant fungus.^[1,9] species which is one of the reasons for minimal antifungal activity of *Padmak Agad*.

As at maximum possible **concentration** minimal activity was observed so, no lower concentrations were tried as of Fluconazole. (Padmak Agad 0.55% W/V, Fluconazole 0.02% W/V)

Due to filtration method the many of non-water-soluble constituents could not participate in the activity assay. Hence, this activity can't be said as for whole compound.

Due to the autoclave method of sterilization which have hampered the thermolabile chemical constituents showing minimal antifungal activity of *Padmak Agad*.

Krumi correlation with dermatophytosis

“*kram+inn ata itwam*”,

Sanskrit-Hindi Kosh Raj Sanskaran

By V. S. Apte

The one who possess series that is *Krumi*.

As per *Charakacharya*, there are some *krimi* invading the blood are not visible with eyes.

“*Sukshmatwaccha bhavantyadrushyaha*”

Ch.Vi.7/11

Sushrutacharya has mentioned

Keshad, rom, nakhad, dantad, kikkisha krumi as Adrushya means invisible,

“*Keshadadyastvadrushyaste*”

.....*Su.U.54/20*

Hence, *krumi* can be correlated with fungi. *Krumi* is also enlisted as causative factor in *Kushtha.Padmak Agad* combinely having *katu ras ushna veerya katu vipak* which are opposite of *Krumijanan Ras, veerya, vipak* that is, *tikta katu, Ushna, katu*.^[17]

Fig. 4: Probable mode of action of *padmak Agad* –(original).

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